

STUDY ON THE PHYSIOGRAPHY DEVISION AND GENERAL LAND USE OF DISTRICT SOLAN HIMACHAL PRADESH

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Abstract

The general height of study area Solan district is located between 221 meters to 2253 meters above sea level. The Sutlej basin region is characterized by rough and hilly patterns. It is situated between 951 meters to 1985 meters above sea level, in which a high mountain range Devi Dhar is located. Solan is spread over the central part of the Lesser Himalayan District. The altitude of this range ranges from 539 meters to 2069 meters above sea level. Nalagarh Shivalik region lies between 221 meters to 1391 meters in the low mountain range. Depending on the study area, different types of features have been elucidated in the study area: (i) Sirsa Valley Tract 2. Sirsa Upland 3. Gambhar Valley Tract 4. Gambhar Upland 5. Satluj Valley Tract 6. Koshalia Valley Tract 7. Ghaggar Valley Tract 8. Asani Valley Tract 9. Asani Upland. Land use is generally classified into four major divisions : forest area (11.21 percent), Cultivable-Waste Land (16.66 percent), Non Cultivable-Waste Land (50.98 percent) and Arable land (21.15 percent).

Key word: Physiography devision and landuse district solan

INTRODUCTION

STUDY AREA

Solan as an independent District came into existence on 1st September, 1972, consequent upon reorganization of the districts of Himachal Pradesh. The District derives its name from Solan, the headquarter town. It is said that the name Solan is associated with Shoolini the local deity, located at a distance of 48 Kms. From Shimla,

Solan is considered as the gateway to capital of Himachal Pradesh. The total area of the district is 1936 sq. km. The district has 7 towns and 2551 villages of these 2348 villages are inhabited. At the 2011 census the total population of the district was 576670. The people of Solan district are predominantly Hindus followed by Sikhs and Muslims. The district lies between north latitude 30°45'11" to 31°22'55" and east longitude 76°36'15" to 77°15'22" and is covered by Survey of India degree-sheets 1:250,000 (53A, 53B, 53E and 53F) and 1:50,000 (53A/12, 53A/15, 53A/16, 53B/9, 53B/13, 53E/3, 53E/4, 53F/1, 53F/2, 53F/5). The district is bounded by Bilaspur district in north-west and Mandi district in the north, Shimla and Sirmour districts in east and south-east respectively. District has inter-state boundary in the south and west with State of Haryana and Punjab respectively. The district is well connected by rail and road network. The nearest airports are at Shimla (Jubbal Hatti) and Chandigarh. Administratively, Solan town is the Head Quarter of the district. The district comprises of 4 sub-divisions viz., Arki, Kandaghat, Nalagarh and Solan and has 6 Tehsils (Arki, Baddi, Kandaghat, Kasauli, Nalagarh and Solan) and 2 sub-tehsils (Krishangarh and Ramshahar). For development purpose, the district has been divided into five community development blocks viz., Dharampur, Kandaghat, Kunihar, Nalagarh and Solan, 198 Gram Panchayats. Important towns in the district are Solan, Nalagarh, Kasauli, Subathu, Dagshai, Arki, Kandaghat, Parwanoo etc. The population of the district is 5, 80, 320 (2011 census), out of which 3,08,754 (53 %) are males, and the rest 2,71,566 (47%) are female. Sex ratio (F:M) is 880:1000 and density of population is 300 per sq km. The rural and urban population is 82.40% and 17.60% respectively. The local inhabitants mainly depend on agriculture for their subsistence and adopt several traditional practices conducive for farming in sloping terrain. Fig. 1

Fig. 1

GEOLOGY

Solan District lying within the Lesser Himalaya and the Shivalik foothill comprises rocks ranging in age from Proterozoic to Quaternary. The oldest rocks of undifferentiated proterozoic age belong to the Jutogh group comprising carbonaceous phyllite, Schist, Gneiss, Quartzite and marble. The Sundernagar group of Rocks of Meso-Preterozoic age represented by quartzite with basic flows. The Deoban/Shali

Group of Rocks (Meso-Proterozoic) Comprising limestone, dolomite, (at Places tromatolytic) Slate & Quartzite occurs along the Main Boundary fault and also in the North-eastern part of the District. The argillo-arenaceous sequence of Shimla/ Jaunsur Group rests unconformable over the Deoban Group and assigned meso-Proterozoic age. Both Shimla and Jaunsaur Group, comprising diamictite, pink dolomite, carbonaceous shale and slate besides quartzite bands. The Krol Group, which overlies the Balaini Group, is dominantly a carbonaceous sequence with minor shale and sandstone. Fig. 2

PHYSIOGRAPHY DIVISION

The District was carved out of Solan and Arki Tehsils of the then Mahasu District and Tehsils of Kandaghat and Nalagarh of the then Shimla District. The District is bounded by Mandi and Bilaspur Districts in the North, Punjab State in the West, Haryana State and Sirmour District in the South and Shimla District in the East. The terrain of the District is mostly mountainous with an elevation ranging from 221 to 2253 Mtrs. above mean sea level. The highest peak in the District is Krol Tibba having the elevation of 2253 Mtrs. above mean sea level. For administrative convenience, the District has been divided into four subdivisions with headquarters at Solan, Kandaghat, Nalagarh and Arki. Solan Sub-division consists of Solan and Kasauli Tehsils and Krishangarh sub-Tehsil, Nalagarh sub-division consists of Nalagarh Tehsil and Ramshaher Sub-Tehsil, whereas Kandaghat and Arki subdivisions cover respective Tehsil only. The terrain is mostly mountainous except valley of Saproon in Solan, Tehsil Doon in Nalagarh Tehsil and Kunihar in Arki Tehsil. The mountains of lower elevations are found in Western and Southern parts of the District comprising of Nalagarh and Arki Tehsils while higher ranges start from Central region and extend up to North-Eastern corner of the District comprising Solan. Kasauli, Kandaghat and parts of Arki Tehsil, Mangal and Berrel Panchayats of Arki Tehsil are situated on a very high mountain ranges and difficult terrain. District of Solan is covered by catchments area of three important rivers namely Satluj, Yamuna and Ghaggar. Main tributary of Yamuna is Asni and those of Satluj River are Kiar-Ka-Nala, Ghamber Khad, and Kuthar Nadi etc.

Fig. 2

Kaushalya Nadi is the main tributary of Ghagar. Sirsa is the main stream in Nalagarh Sub-Division. It has its source in the Hill above Kalka and runs North-West along the base of the Shivalik eventually joining the Satluj at Avankot in Ropar Distt. The branching drainage pattern so established is tree like, is termed as dendrite drainage pattern. The study area to divide in 9 Physiographic division : 1. Sirsa Valley Tract (221-625 Miter) 2. Sirsa Upland (285-1350 Miter) 3. Gambhar Valley Tract (550-1350

Miter) 4. Gambhar Upland (750-2050 Miter) 5. Satluj Valley Tract (951-1983 Miter) 6. Koshallaa Valley Tract (750-2000 Miter) 7. Ghaggar Valley Tract (500-2050 Miter) 8. Asani Valley Tract (1500-2000 Miter) 9. Asani Upland (1000-2250 Miter) Fig. 3

LAND USE PATTERN

The District is spread over the valleys and higher elevations. The cultivation is possible only in small terraces in the hills or along the stream/ Khad in most parts of the District. However, in the valleys the cultivation is spread over a vast area. Except the valley area most of the land is either under shrub forests or grassy land with chill trees up to the height of 1,500 Mtrs. from the mean sea level and Kail and Deodar on the high altitudes. It is only in the Doon, Saproon and Kunihar valleys that the land is mostly flat and fertile. The settlement operations in the District were carried out at different times as most of the area was forming the princely hill States. Agriculture is the main stay of the rural economy of the District 54.96 percent of the working population of the District is engaged in agriculture. Maize, Wheat, Rice and Pulses etc. are the main crops of the District. Cash crops such as sugarcane in Nalagarh Tehsil and Potato in Kandaghat Tehsil are grown. Besides, vegetable cultivation has also taken a boost. Despite hilly topography of the District additional area has been brought under cultivation. A large number of cultivators in the District are growing mushroom on commercial scale, as the climatic conditions in the District are most conducive for growing mushrooms, special incentives are being offered to small and marginal farmers. The soil in the district varies from light to sandy heavy and in the valley areas it is sandy loam types of soil. Climate is the main factors responsible for the proper development of agriculture in the area. The district has different type of soils, which offer great potentialities for growing various types of cereals, fruits, vegetables and other cash crops. Climate of the District Is mostly sub tropical in the lower reaches and moist temperature in upper reaches. Table : 1, 2

Fig. 3

The hilly and agro-climatic condition of the district is very congenial for the development of the horticulture in general and cultivation of temperate and stone fruits in particular. Apart from stone and citrus fruits, apples are also being grown in the higher reaches of the district and its cultivation is mainly in Chail area of Kandaghat Tehsil. Fig. 4

Table 1 : Solan District Landuse (2010-2011)

Landuse	2000-2001		2010-2011		Total Change (%)
	Area (ha)	Percentage	Area (ha)	Percentage	
Forest	20290	11.40	20279	11.21	-0.05
Cultivable-Waste Land	27147	15.26	30144	16.66	+11.04
Non Cultivable-Waste Land	91479	51.41	92234	59.98	+0.82
Arable Land	39007	21.92	38266	21.15	-1.19
Total	177923	100.00	180923	100.00	+1.69

Source : District Sensus Solan 2011

Table 2 : Solan District Landuse pattern (2010-2011)

Landuse pattern (Ha)

Tehsil/ Sub Tehsil	Area	Forest area		Cultivable-Waste Land		Non Cultivable-Waste Land		Arable Land	
		Area	(%)	Area	(%)	Area	(%)	Area	(%)
Arki	39403	6939	17.61	3614	9.17	20332	51.60	8518	21.62
Kandaghat	20722	495	2.39	3094	14.93	14289	68.95	2844	13.72
Kasauli	13883	292	2.10	3056	22.01	7311	52.66	3224	23.22
Krishnagarh	15249	2178	14.28	1689	11.08	9085	59.58	2297	15.06
Nalagarh	52291	7317	13.99	11869	22.69	17906	34.24	15199	29.07
Ramshahar	18322	2617	14.28	2617	14.28	10270	56.05	2818	15.38
Solan	21053	441	2.09	4205	19.97	13041	61.94	3366	15.99
Grant Total	180923	20279	11.21	30144	16.66	92234	50.98	38266	21.15

Source : District Sensus Solan 2011

Fig. 4

Due to wide variations in the altitude, soil depth and available moisture, the vegetation met within this division shows a great variation. Chil, Khair, Bamboos and other broad leaved species like Chhal, Simbal, Jhingan etc. are the most important species met within this area. Tropical Euphorbia scrub forest to Shiwalik Chil, pine and little Ban oak forests are found in this area. Vegetation changes due to water and slopes. Undergrowth consists of Phullakri, Karaunda, Ghandela and top storey consists of Kashmal, Katni, Kainth, Tirmira, Khair, Bel, Banarasi, Kangu, Malkora, Dub, Dhaula and lobb are the various types of grasses found in this District. The climbers that are generally found are Hedera Lelix, Smilax, Bauhnia vehili, Smilax spp, Gulab, Acacia Pinnata etc. There is a great variety of wild life met within this District. The main wild life animals found are; Leopard, Ghoral, Indian wild Bear, Kakar, Hyena, Wild bear, Porcupine, Hone, Squirrels. Leopard is found throughout the area up to an elevation of about 2,200mtrs. In scrub forests Ghoral is found above an elevation of 1200mtrs. In Mangal area various types of birds like Chukar, Black Petridge, Kaleshna and Jungle fowl are also found in the District. Besides the already mentioned birds, a number of other birds like Peacock, Parrot, Sparrow, Pigeon and Doves are also found. The entire tract of Kunihar forest falls in Satluj catchment.

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